

“It’s a Bit Like Going to McDonald’s – In the Moment You Feel Satisfied, You Feel Great, But an Hour Later You are Hungry”:

Mathematics Teachers’ Views of Professional Development in Ireland

Jillian White, Patrick Johnson and Merrilyn Goos

University of Limerick

This paper details the results of a study that aims to reimagine the professional development offered to Irish secondary school mathematics teachers. This reimaged design will be based on four perspectives, one of which is that of current mathematics teachers in the Irish context. It is this perspective that is the subject of this paper. Through a series of semi-structured interviews and a follow-up national survey, teachers expressed their opinions on what professional development should and shouldn’t entail. These opinions can be grouped into the following themes: the role of the internet in professional development; the provision and sharing of teaching and learning resources; having opportunities to discuss teaching approaches and pedagogy styles with colleagues; engagement with and access to professional development; professional development activities; the facilitator; and the role of professional conversations in teachers’ continued professional development.

The Role of Teacher Professional Development

The endeavour to ensure that mathematics is accessible for all communities of learners is a noble one. It is linked, however, with the ongoing professional development of those in the role of “teacher” within these communities to ensure they remain equipped with the skills and knowledge necessary to meet the needs of their mathematics learners and create an environment that allows for meaningful learning for all. After graduation from their initial teacher education programmes, professional development opportunities are often the only form of formal education teachers experience in relation to how they teach. As such, Desimone et al. (2002) credit professional development as a crucial mechanism to increase and enhance teacher knowledge and teacher classroom practices. Additionally, Flecknoe (2000) found that teachers developed constructive attitudes towards both their subject and the act of teaching after engaging in professional development, and the students of those teachers who experimented with new strategies and practices introduced at a professional development programme increased their desire to learn. In the subject area of mathematics, Smith (2004) witnessed increased levels of motivation and enthusiasm among teachers who had engaged in particular professional development programmes.

When conducted effectively, professional development has the potential to challenge teachers and assist them to develop new skills. In an ever-changing world, teachers need to adapt how they teach to adequately prepare their students for further education, work and life in general. This requires teachers to understand both teaching and learning, address the particular needs of students, and connect students’ experiences with the goals of the curriculum (Darling-Hammond, 2005). Developing, changing, and improving one’s instructional practice is therefore a life-long (or career-long) endeavour and requires the

assistance of various, effective professional development opportunities. The research project discussed in this paper sought to investigate the professional development available to Irish mathematics teachers from four perspectives – the theoretical and experimental literature perspective, the international experience perspective, the policy perspective, and the perspective of current Irish mathematics teachers. The aim of the project was to design a reimagined model of professional development that incorporates and aligns with each of these four perspectives. It is the understanding gained from the fourth perspective that will be the subject of this paper. First, however, a brief overview of the definition of effective professional development will be provided.

Defining Effective Professional Development for Teachers

While research suggests that teacher professional development is crucial for the improvement of systems, schools, and student achievement, some argue that the term *professional development* is conceptually vague (Coffield, 2000) and the concept ambiguous and contested (Friedman & Phillips, 2004). Hoban (2002) encourages separation of the terms *professional development* and *professional learning* while Wei et al. (2009) describe professional development as a subset of professional learning. Wei and colleagues conceptualise professional learning as the product of any activity that results in an increase in teacher knowledge or a change in teacher practice, while they refer to professional development as the activities that are formal, planned, and aim to impact a teacher's professional learning when designed. It is this distinction and definition that will be used throughout this paper. This definition of professional development does not include unplanned experiences that happen to result in professional learning, although the authors do recognise the importance of these instances.

There is a broad consensus in the field of education research on the characteristics of effective professional development. Knapp (2003) summarises the work of many by providing the following list of six essential characteristics that increase the probability that a professional development activity impacts the classroom practices of a participating teacher. Knapp (2003) argues that professional development opportunities should:

1. Concentrate on classroom teaching that emphasizes high learning standards and on evidence of students' learning to standard.
2. Focus on building teacher's pedagogical content knowledge.
3. Model "preferred" instructional practices (e.g. active learning), both in classrooms and in adult learning situations.
4. Locate professional learning in collaborative, collegial – and generally school-based – learning environments.
5. Offer rigorous and cumulative opportunities for professional learning over time.
6. Align with reform initiatives. (pp. 119-120)

Unfortunately, there is a lack of alignment between much of the professional development on offer to Irish mathematics teachers and what are deemed best practices in this regard. The professional development opportunities that are most widely available to Irish

mathematics teachers are generic workshops, a model of professional development that has been shown to be often ineffective due the lack of connection to teachers' individual contexts and practices (Hawley & Valley, 1999). Therefore, Irish mathematics teachers are in urgent need of a restructured and reimagined model of professional development, a model which this wider research project aims to understand and develop. In order to create such a model, the opinions and experiences of current Irish mathematics teachers were sought to ensure that teacher voice was central to the redesigned model and that the model aligns with the needs and wants of current Irish mathematics teachers. As outlined earlier, this perspective is one of four perspectives that will be incorporated into the final design, but it is the results from this teacher perspective that will outlined in the remainder of this paper.

Gathering and Analysing the Perspectives of Current Irish Mathematics Teachers

In October 2020 an invitation was sent to all secondary school mathematics teachers in Ireland, via their school administrators' email, to partake in a semi-structured interview on the topic of professional development. In this email, teachers were provided with three questions that would form the core structure of the interview so that they would have time to consider their responses prior to the recorded phone interview. These three questions were:

1. In what area of mathematics teaching/curriculum reform would you like to receive support as a maths teacher?
2. What provisions/supports/forms/types of professional development would be most helpful for you in your role as a maths teacher?
3. What forms/types of professional development do you currently engage with in your role as a maths teacher? What has been your recent experience with professional development? How helpful has this been for you as a maths teacher?

Between October 2020 and January 2021, 24 teachers were interviewed. Each interview was audio recorded and transcribed. A thematic analysis was conducted on the interview transcripts using Braun and Clarke's (2006) phases of thematic analysis as follows:

1. Each interview was read and reread.
2. On the second reading the content of each interview was summarised into a series of "I" statements.
3. Related or similar statements from all teachers were placed together.
4. Related or similar statements were rewritten as a single statement along with a frequency count to show how many teachers this new statement linked with.
5. Similarly themed statements were then grouped and a theme name chosen.
6. Theme names and statements were read and reread.
7. Overly similar theme names and statements were combined until a final list of distinct themes and statements remained.

Following this thematic analysis, the resulting statements were collated into a survey. Surveyed teachers were asked to respond via a Likert scale of agreement/disagreement. The purpose of the survey was to determine what proportion of a broader number of teachers agreed or disagreed with the views of the 24 interviewed teachers. When the survey was

piloted, pilot participants stated that the survey was too long. As a result, all statements that related to the views of only one interviewed teacher were removed, with 52 statements remaining in the final document. In late February 2021, the final survey was sent to all secondary school teachers of mathematics in the 730 secondary schools in Ireland via their school administrator's email. 160 responses were received. An overview of the results of these interviews and the follow up survey are provided in the next section.

Results: Professional Development from the Perspective of Irish Mathematics Teachers

Both the interviews and follow up survey sent to teachers had three main sections that aligned with the three interview questions – in summary, what teachers would like professional development to focus on, what teachers would like professional development to look like, and what teachers' recent experiences with professional development had been. The latter two categories were inherently linked as many interviewed teachers used their recent experiences with professional development to describe what they would and would not like to experience in future professional development opportunities. Due to the short nature of this paper, it is only these two categories that will be discussed. The following subsections outline the results of the interview process in the form of the statements that emerged from the thematic analysis. In addition, the results of the follow-up survey, in the form of the percentage of surveyed teachers that either agreed or strongly agreed with each statement, are provided in the brackets. Each subsection is a theme that emerged from the interview data.

Online Professional Development Opportunities

The theme of “online professional development” and the role the internet could, can, and does play in the professional development opportunities available to mathematics teachers was discussed by 17 of the 24 interviewed teachers. The common views expressed by two or more of these teachers were summarised into the following five statements:

- I would benefit from all professional development opportunities for maths teachers being advertised and/or available on a single website (91%).
- I would benefit from professional development that is offered online (85%).
- An increase in the amount of professional development opportunities offered online would make professional development more accessible to me (82%).
- I would benefit from having access to recorded online professional development that I can engage with at my own convenience (88%).
- I would like to have access to online "refresher" videos where Leaving Certificate higher level mathematical concepts are explained (78%).

Teaching and Learning Resources

The theme of “teaching and learning resources” was discussed by 18 of the 24 interviewed teachers. This theme encompasses concepts such as the sharing of resources among teachers, being provided with resources at professional development opportunities, and the lack of resources available in some schools. The common views expressed by two or more of these teachers were summarised into the following seven statements:

- I would benefit professionally from opportunities to share resources with other maths teachers (85%).
- I am more likely to use resources presented at professional development opportunities in my teaching if I am provided with the resource at the end of the professional development opportunity (89%).
- I am more likely to use resources presented at professional development opportunities if the presentation includes evidence of the resources being used in a school setting (84%).
- I would benefit from access to a bank of resources online that teachers could both download and add to and share their experiences of implementing the resources in a comments section attached to the particular resource (92%).
- I am more likely to use resources presented at professional development opportunities in my teaching if the resources are easily accessible online (94%).
- I am more likely to use resources/activities presented at professional development opportunities if they take less than 10 minutes to do in class and are easy to implement (78%).
- I feel that those facilitating professional development opportunities need to be more aware of the limited resources available in many schools (84%).

Teaching Approaches and Pedagogy Sharing

The theme of “teaching approaches and pedagogy sharing” was discussed by 15 of the 24 interviewed teachers. This theme most often appeared when teachers were discussing what they would like their professional development to consist of, rather than what they are currently engaging in. The common views expressed by two or more of the interviewed teachers were summarised into the following four groups of statements:

- I would like to engage in professional development where teachers gather to share how they currently teach a particular topic, with a variety of approaches being discussed (77%).
- I would be willing to share my own approaches with teachers from my own school (88%).
- I would be willing to share my own approaches with teachers from a number of schools (73%).
- Following the sharing of ideas, I would like time to trial these ideas in my classroom before gathering with this group of teachers again to discuss my experience (78%).
- I would benefit from in-school professional development consisting of regular department meetings where we share ideas, try out changes and then report back to one another on our experience (78%).
- Having access to a large number of sample lessons or resources related to a particular pedagogy/approach to teaching would help me better implement this pedagogy/approach into my classroom on an ongoing basis (85%).

Engagement and Access

The theme of “engagement and access” was discussed by 20 of the 24 interviewed teachers. This theme consists of topics relating to when, where, and with whom teachers would like to engage in professional development opportunities. The common views expressed by two or more of the interviewed teachers were summarised into the following six statements:

- I am willing to engage with professional development outside of the normal school day (68%).
- I would like professional development opportunities to be facilitated more regularly than they currently are (81%).
- I would like for my entire mathematics department to have the opportunity to engage in professional development as a group (83%).
- I would benefit from a broader range of professional development opportunities being offered (71%).
- I would be more motivated to engage in professional development opportunities if management in my school designated a specific time (during or after the school day) when all teachers were to engage in professional development of some sort (73%).
- I would be more likely to engage in professional development if time spent engaging counted towards my Croke Park hours (88%).

Professional Development Activities

The theme of “professional development activities” was discussed by 14 of the 24 interviewed teachers. This theme consists of topics relating to what teachers would like to do, and with whom, during professional development opportunities. The common views expressed by two or more of the interviewed teachers were summarised into the following four statements:

- I benefit more from professional development that allows me to engage with and trial the resources or ideas being presented throughout the opportunity (79%).
- If engaging in group work at a professional development opportunity, I would benefit most from being grouped with teachers from my own school or from schools that are similar to my own (71%).
- All content presented at professional development opportunities should be grounded in research and be deemed a best practice principle (75%).
- I would benefit from the opportunity to witness (either in person or online) a fellow teacher teaching (70%).

Facilitator of Professional Development Opportunities

The theme of “facilitator” was discussed by 14 of the 24 interviewed teachers. This theme consists of topics relating to who teachers would like to facilitate professional development opportunities, what experience they would like this person to have, and what this person could do to make the opportunity as beneficial as possible. The common views

expressed by two or more of the interviewed teachers were summarised into the following six statements:

- I would prefer for professional development opportunities to be led by experienced maths teachers with an extensive knowledge of the content/idea being presented and/or discussed (89%).
- If something novel is being presented at a professional development opportunity the presenter must be an expert in that particular field (74%).
- The facilitator of the professional development opportunity must be knowledgeable about the realities of current classrooms and pitch their ideas at an appropriate level (95%).
- It is important to me that the facilitator of the professional development opportunity is open to questions and facilitating discussions (94%).
- I would benefit from the facilitator modelling the approaches being discussed with the teachers present acting as the students (63%).
- Professional development opportunities would be more beneficial if all providers (e.g. PDST, Education Centres, IMTA, universities) worked together and presented a common message (89%).

Professional Conversations

The theme of “professional conversations” was discussed by 14 of the 24 interviewed teachers. This theme consists of topics relating to how teachers benefit from the opportunity to converse with colleagues from their own school and from other schools and how they would appreciate more organised times to engage in these conversations. The common views expressed by two or more of the interviewed teachers were summarised into the following three statements:

- I benefit from conversations with teachers from different schools about the content being presented when attending professional development opportunities (83%).
- I would benefit professionally from having regular group meetings with the other maths teachers in my school to ask questions and collaborate on resources and ideas (84%).
- I would be more likely to transfer knowledge gained from a professional development opportunity back into my classroom if I was given time the next day to discuss this knowledge with my department colleagues and plan for the implementation given our school context (81%).

Conclusions & Next Steps

Throughout the interview and survey processes, Irish secondary school mathematics teachers have been very clear on what they want in relation to professional development. The high levels of agreement among the surveyed teachers suggests that the views of the interviewed teachers are shared by a wider proportion of secondary school mathematics teachers in Ireland. These views are not dissimilar to the literature on best practice regarding teacher professional development, however these teachers have provided details regarding the

opportunities, activities, characteristics, and supports that would allow these best practice principles to be translated into the Irish education system effectively. In order to progress the requests made by teachers, these results will be combined with what are deemed best practices by the theoretical and experimental literature in the field, the experiences of professional development developers internationally, and the Irish education policy relating to the professional development of secondary school mathematics teachers. Collaboration with the main teacher professional development stakeholders will then need to begin to ensure that meaningful, impactful professional development is accessible to all secondary school teachers of mathematics in Ireland.

References

- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77-101.
- Coffield, F. (2000). Introduction: A critical analysis of the concept of a learning society. In F. Coffield (Ed.), *Differing visions of a learning society*. Policy Press.
- Darling-Hammond, L. (2005). Developing professional development schools: Early lessons, challenge, and promise. In L. Darling-Hammond (Ed.), *Professional development schools: Schools for developing a profession* (pp. 1-27). Teachers College Press.
- Desimone, L., Porter, A., Garet, M., Yoon, K., & Birman, B. (2002). Effects of professional development on teachers' instruction: Results from a three-year longitudinal study. *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis*, 24(2), 81-112.
- Flecknoe, M. (2000). Can continuing professional development for teachers be shown to raise pupils' achievement? *Journal of In-Service Education*, 26(3), 436-457.
- Friedman, A., & Phillips, M. (2004). Continuing professional development: Developing a vision. *Journal of Education and Work*, 17(3), 361-376.
- Hawley, W. D., & Valli, L. (1999). The essentials of effective professional development. In L. Darling-Hammond and G. Sykes (Eds.), *Teaching as the learning profession: Handbook of policy and practice* (pp. 127-150). Jossey-Bass.
- Hoban, G. F. (2002). *Teacher learning for educational change*. Open University Press.
- Knapp, M. S. (2003). Professional development as policy pathway. *Review of Research in Education*, 27(1), 109-157.
- Smith, A. (2004). *Making mathematics count: The report of Professor Adrian Smith's inquiry into post-14 mathematics education*. Retrieved July 22, 2020
<https://dera.ioe.ac.uk/4873/>
- Wei, R. C., Darling-Hammond, L., Andree, A., Richardson, N., & Orphanos, S. (2009). *Professional learning in the learning profession: A status report on teacher development in the United States and abroad*. National Staff Development Council.

The background consists of several overlapping colored rectangles. A yellow rectangle is at the top left. A large light blue rectangle covers the top and middle sections. A yellow rectangle is on the left side, overlapping the blue one. A brown rectangle is positioned horizontally, overlapping the blue and yellow rectangles. A red rectangle is at the bottom right, overlapping the brown and yellow rectangles.

MEI 8
Institute of Education,
Dublin City University
2021